

Open Source Software in Data Science - Survey (5 Bonus Points)

This study tries to elicit some insight on the culture of Open Source software development. When referring to Open Source software, in the context of this study, we are NOT thinking of major software initiatives such as e.g. the Linux Operating System, Open Office, the Apache Framework, TensorFlow, etc. that are created and maintained by large consortia of developers.

Rather, the focus is on individual libraries and specific solutions that are contributed by individuals or small groups of people. Examples include specific implementations of data pre-processing routines, specific machine learning algorithms, evaluation code, visualizations, as shared on e.g. *GitHub*, or solutions to specific problems as shared on e.g. *StackExchange* and similar discussion fora. The study tries to elicit how you act with respect to such Open Source Software components or code snippets posted as answers, or what you observe in the community.

Note that you will NOT be evaluated on the actual content of the answers that you give. The evaluation will be anonymized (We only need the link to your student ID to give you the bonus points). We thus specifically are not looking for answers that reflect how things should be done in an ideal world, given infinite amounts of time and resources, but rather on how you personally do things - even if you are aware that this is not optimal, given the constraints in both university schedules and professional life.

The results will be used as part of a PhD research project evaluating the broader scope of styles of work in research and the impact of research infrastructures.

-----WORK-----

1. **(Work)** Do you - next to your university studies - also work professionally in a related domain, performing data analytics, writing code for a company, etc.?
2. **(Work - type)** If so, could you briefly characterize your type of work in a few words (without mentioning the actual company)?
3. **(Experience)** How many years of experience in the field (doing analytics, writing code, using libraries, ...) do you have?
4. **(Activities)** Main Activities/Expertise: Please provide some examples on what you have been working on, whether as part of your university studies, or job, where you came in contact with Open Source code. (specific assignments, Programming Languages, etc.)

-----SHARING-----

5. **(OS-provided)** Have you already provided open source code yourself via dedicated repositories such as Github or posted solutions on fora such as Stackexchange etc.?
 - a. very frequently

- b. occasionally
 - c. only when required to do so
 - d. never so far
- 6. (Code examples)** If so, which type of code/functionality/modules have you provided as project owner or contributor? Please, list a few examples.
- 7. (Code examples)** What motivates you to provide your code as Open Source? If you have never provided code open source (or only when required to do so), what are some of the reasons for this?
- 8. (Providing Source Code (Pressure))** Do you feel more pressure with respect to code quality, testing, providing comments and documentation, etc. when you have to share source code publicly?
- a. Yes
 - b. Not at all
 - i. Can you explain your answer above? What is the source of additional pressure if there is any (internal/external)? How strong is it? How much additional effort does it cause?
 - ii. How well do you feel you meet this (self-imposed?) pressure? Why / Why not?
- 9. (Testing I)** Do you document and test your code more intensively when you intend to share it?
- a. Yes
 - b. No
- 10. (Testing II)** How do you test your code or code-snippets posted in fora before sharing/posting?
- 11. (Testing III)** Which additional tests, quality assurance measures, etc. would you like to apply but usually lack time to do so?
- 12. (Testing IV)** Do you usually provide any additional information such as test data, unit tests, test protocols etc. as part of the documentation when you release source code? If so, which ones and to what extent?
- 13. (Updates)** Do you usually provide updates to code / release versions / correct code snippets you posted?
- a. Frequently
 - b. Sometimes
 - c. Hardly ever
 - d. Never needed to do so
 - e. Never - I rarely/never revisit most projects shared / answers posted
- 14. (Updates - Type)** When you provide updates, these include usually:
- a. Fixing bugs
 - b. Adding functionality
 - c. Improving documentation
 - d. Improving code stability, scalability
 - e. Fixing dependencies

f. Other

15. (Testing V) How do you decide when you have done a sufficient amount of testing such to release the code (either Open Source or just "submit")?

16. (Testing VI) How confident are you that, after testing, your code is bug-free?

- a. absolutely sure
- b. very confident
- c. rather confident, only bugs not affecting the functionality / correctness of the computation
- d. some bugs left that may affect the functionality
- e. pretty sure that there are several bugs left to be fixed that affect the core functionality

-----REUSE-----

17. (Reuse I) How frequently are you using open source libraries, modules, code, code snippets posted on discussion fora, etc. for your own projects/work?

- a. constantly
- b. every now and then
- c. whenever required to do so
- d. never
 - i. If so: which ones? Please provide a few typical examples of the type/scope of libraries, functions from repositories or solutions looked for / taken from discussion fora:

18. (Choice of modules) In case there are several alternatives to choose from that offer similar / identical functionality, which criteria do you use to decide which one to select?

19. (Reuse II) Why do you base your decision on these criteria?

20. (Reuse III) How confident are you, that the modules you select for re-use are bug-free in their basic functionality?

- a. Absolutely sure
- b. Quite confident
- c. I hope they are
- d. Not confident at all

21. (Reuse IV) How do you tell? What aspects influence your judgement?

-----QUALITY ASSESSMENT-----

22. (Quality Assessment I) In your opinion, what are good quality indicators to be confident that the source code is solid, (sufficiently) bug-free?

- a. Frequency of commits
- b. Most recent commit
- c. Type of commits / commit messages
- d. Number of contributors
- e. Number of downloads
- f. Number and types of references to the project / code
- g. Age of the project

- h. Availability of test runs and test protocols
 - i. Comments in the forum
 - j. Documentation and tutorials
 - i. Others: If so, which?
- 23. (Quality Assessment I)** How would you order the above in terms of importance?
- 24. (Quality Assessment I)** Please, do explain why you think they are good quality markers:
- 25. (Quality Assessment I)** To what extent do you think these are good indicators for the quality of the code?
- 26. (Quality Assessment I)** Are you usually testing the modules, libraries etc. before reusing them in your own projects?
- a. Yes
 - i. How are you testing them?
 - b. No
 - i. Why not?
- 27. (Quality Assessment II)** Given enough time and resources, how would you test code before using it in your own projects? What would be useful components to have?
- a. Test data provided by the creator of the software
 - b. Your own test data where you know the output that the software should produce
 - c. Unit tests provided as part of the code
 - d. Test protocols
- 28. (Quality Assessment II)** Please, elaborate on the type of quality checks and tests you usually apply, and which ones you would like to apply if you had enough time and resources.

-----TRUST-----

- 29. (Trust - extent)** Assuming that there might be errors left in the code you are using (both self-created and from third-party libraries): To what extent do you usually trust your own results / output you produce (on a scale between 0-100)?
- 30. (Trust - justify)** How would you argue the extent of trust given above? Does it vary across your projects and why / in which form?
- 31. (Penalty)** How high a fine / payment for damages (in Euro) would you accept to pay (personally, or via the company that employs you) for faulty results of the solution you provided? (Minimal: 0)
- 32. (Penalty - justify)** How would you justify the amount of financial liability you have specified? How much does it vary across your projects? What would influence the amount? Do you see a difference between personal liability/accountability and that of your employer?
- 33. (Trust - reputation)** How important is loss of reputation due to erroneous results? How does it compare to any financial liabilities?

-----OTHER-----

- 34. (Difference uni - job)** In the answers above, do you see a major difference between the research you do as part of your university degree program (e.g. your Bachelor / Master thesis) and the work you do professionally (your current or future job)?
- 35. (Feedback - other)** Do you have any other comments regarding this survey, aspects that influence trust and re-use of code and data, from your perspective?